

NEGATIVE IMPACT OF DISCRIMINATORY FACTORS ON MOBILE AND ADAPTIVE RELATIONSHIPS OF STUDENTS

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Abstract. *In this article, the current discriminatory approach in the education system and its negative impact on students are analyzed from psychological aspects, negative consequences in the preparation of mobile individuals, pedagogical-psychological factors that cause existing problems in the life of society, and social pedagogical-psychological proposals scientific opinions are expressed.*

Keywords: *education, flexibility, discrimination, mobile, student, teacher, educational institution, psychological mechanism, sphere of influence, motivation, innovation.*

The concept that a healthy psychological climate prevails in every vapor and sphere of society, as in all periods, is considered inappropriate. The reason is that an impartial and cordial attitude is not properly established, in addition to the confrontation of interests that generate internal conflicts. In most cases, the interaction does not take into account the human psyche and its effectiveness. As a result, the psychological trauma of our behavior and attitude, its negative consequences, has always been ignored and remains. The relevance of the development and implementation of socio-psychological programs related to the mechanisms of scientific research, prevention and elimination of such issues is growing today. From this point of view, the relevance of the topic that we are analyzing and reacting scientifically is one of the issues that are currently waiting for a social solution for the life of society. The need for novel approaches to the in-depth study of some aspects of traditional foundations in the activities and interaction of individuals in the life of society, as well as a mobile and flexible attitude mechanism that meets psychological and spiritual needs.

The discriminatory approach under this study is that discrimination and segregation cause citizens to violate their rights and freedoms, humiliate the honor and dignity of people, manifest themselves in various forms, in particular, manifested during study and recruitment, during educational and labor activities, etc. Article 26 of the Universal Declaration of human rights, adopted on December 10, 1948, put forward procedures and progressive ideas that "education should be aimed at the comprehensive development of the human personality, increasing respect for Human Rights and fundamental freedoms", and included the principle of non-discrimination in the human society and the issue of strengthening the right of The purpose of this can be understood as the fact that the decision-making of a strong civil society in the world should be determined by all states as a goal for their predecessors. For Bning, first of all, they must carry out education and upbringing from a humanism point of view, realizing that each person is responsible for the full implementation of this in society. In the case of discrimination in Kshilik society, it is necessary that all spheres become an integral part of education the psychological mechanisms of the implementation of its vital and humanitarian activities, actions and relations on the basis of the humanitarian principle. Issues have been seen and special documents have been adopted within the UN in relation to the discrimination and response in the education system. Article 1 of the UN Convention, adopted on 14 December 1960, states that "discrimination" is "other beliefs that have

the purpose or effect of ending or disrupting relations in race, color, gender, language, religion, politics or education, to prevent discrimination in matters such as national or social origin, economic status or birth, education...[3]. It should be noted that this Convention clearly defines the possibility of education, the level and quality of education and the conditions for its implementation. Also, to eliminate or prevent discrimination, the responsibility of UN member states is assigned to a number of tasks, which are:

- abolition of all administrative orders and termination of discriminatory administrative practices in the field of Education;

- to eliminate existing discrimination and take the necessary measures in this regard in the process of admission of students to educational institutions;

- to ensure equal access to tuition fees, scholarships and any other assistance provided by the public administration to those educated who are citizens of a particular country;

- to prevent differentiation in the attitude towards education recipients regarding the necessary permits and benefits;

- to create existing legal conditions for the continuation of studies abroad, regardless of their success and needs in education, etc. [2].

Researcher I.Ya.Kiselev's scientific reasoning about the discriminatory approach is significant, and he says in this regard-discrimination belittles the human dignity of those who carry out labor activities, disrupts their consciousness, creates tension in the field of Labor Relations, nourishes the hostility of certain groups towards others, does not comply with the rules of demand and order of socially healthy relations even creates instability on a global scale and The discriminaton approach is included in all spheres of society, and it is advisable to research the dynamic processes of this issue from a scientific point of view. In the field of Education, a comprehensive and in-depth study of this issue should be carried out. To avoid discrimination in education, the teacher is required to have professional knowledge and skills in his field. The researcher who put forward scientific views and theoretical ideas in this regard was S.S.Mutsinov puts forward the following points of view: the professional skills of the teacher – determined not only by the general pedagogical culture, but also by the degree of formation of didactic, communicative, emotional abilities, as well as the development of creative potential. Professors and teachers working at all stages of the educational system are obliged to constantly improve their professional knowledge, qualifications and engage in scientific research. Also, each professor yukasak should have psychological and pedagogical knowledge and pedagogical skills, critical analysis and professional self-improvement, as well as a person of pedagogical Culture[1].

It should be noted that in the educational process, each participant (teacher, student, student) must behave appropriately, feel inclusion in the intellectual layer of society, be an example to others, obey the rules of internal order discipline, etiquette and law. Whether or not this procedure forgets the rules is one of the factors that create an existing conflict discriminatory situation in the educational system. It should be noted that today in some educational system of our country, discriminatory cases in the field of direct or indirect education can be observed. This process is considered one of the social psychological problems that serve to educate young people in the spirit of patriotism and reduce the quality of training specialist personnel. Therefore, it is necessary to identify and timely eliminate the factors that cause such problems. It is necessary to develop modern scientific methods of organizing the educational process, as well as the development, active introduction of technical teaching aids, increase the ethics of teachers and turn

the tomoyil of tolerance into a professional comेतentlg of specialists of all spheres operating in the educational system.

In conclusion, it is advisable to increase the oida requirements for the conscientious fulfillment of training assignments, studying with a high level of discipline, commitment to duty and responsibility from those who receive education. The elimination of a discriminatory approach in the educational system of our society assumes the following implementation:

- in the educational system, information such as “child of an unknown family”, “child of a troubled family”, “internally registered” (this information is open to all students studying under the supervision of teachers operating in some educational institutions) will be provided within the framework of persons and organizations within the competent framework;

- to ensure the fulfillment of the legal obligation and spiritual duty of all educational institutions on the education of their students;

- ensure equally high education in all educational institutions and the conditions necessary for its implementation;

- to discriminate against the teaching profession and not to allow its activities to be interfered with without law;

- real-world implementation of measures within the framework of the law for the education of the teacher (in schools) and for interfering with the educational process;

- Organization of free time for the targeted training of teachers working in the educational system, a fair approach to the implementation of scientific and pedagogical work and the creation of textbooks and teaching aids;

- the introduction of modern technical means (computer technology and other electronic equipment) into the educational process of all educational systems within the framework of their full and need;

- fair implementation of measures developed to improve the quality of Education;

- to give themselves leadership and give motivation, encouraging the authors of the educational and methodological program and Idea related to the training of modern personnel in the educational system;

- development and implementation of a fair criterion for stimulating scientific projects that we carry out in order to highlight and eliminate current problems of our time related to education;

- effective organization of education for professors and teachers and the creation of as comfortable conditions as possible for the performance of professional professional tasks;

- coordination of the mobile and flexible attitude mechanism in the educational system to innovative factors;

- creation and introduction into practice a modern model of ensuring the integration of pedagogical and psychological factors that influence the processes of training of mobile personnel necessary for all spheres in the future, free from discretionary factors.

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